

SELF-CONFIDENCE AND OPENNESS AMONG SPORTSPERSON AND NON-SPORTSPERSON STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to investigate the self-confidence and openness of sportsperson and non- sportsperson in Jalgaon city. Mukta Rani Rasthogi self-concept scale was used to measure self-confidence, COSTA and McCrae 2010 NEO five-factor personality inventory was used to measure the personality factors openness. The sample consists of 100 subjects 50 sportsperson students and 50 non-sportsperson students (50 male, 50 female) between ages rang 18-24 years were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The collected data was analyzed using the Independent sample 't' test. This study found that the sportsperson students have better self-confidence and openness than non- sportsperson students.

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Key word- Self-confidence, Openness, sportsperson and Non- sportsperson students.

Introduction

The present study deals with the self-confidence and openness of the student's Sportsperson and Non-sportsperson. Such research is of great importance in today's competitive world. Psychology is a science in which, we study about human behavior and Sports Psychology is primarily concerned with the analysis of behavior of sports persons. Sports psychology involves the study of how psychological factors affect performance and how participation in sports and exercises affect psychological and physical factors. Concentration, confidence, control, and commitment are generally considered the main psychological qualities that are important for successful performance in sports. Nowadays sports not only require physical skills, but a strong mental game as well.

Sport psychology has emerged as a field with a research tradition that provides a foundation for direct application with athletes. As the role played by psychological factors in the performance and over self-confidence of athletes has become better understood, intervention have been designed to favorably affect athlete behavior throughout their involvement in sport and beyond.

This enforces the researchers to have detail research in this field, further; the researchers feel the need of doing such research to find the relationship between the self-confidence and openness of the student's Sportsperson and Non-sportsperson.

Self-confident is commonly defined as the sureness of feeling that you are equal to the task at hand. This sureness is characterized by absolute belief in ability. You may well know someone whose self-belief has this unshakeable quality. Whose ego resists even the biggest setbacks?

Openness is one of five major domains which are used to describe human personality. Openness involves active imagination, aesthetic sensitivity, attentiveness to inner feelings, preference for variety, and intellectual curiosity. A great deal of psychometric research has demonstrated that these qualities are statistically correlated. Thus, openness can be viewed as a global personality trait consisting of a set of specific traits, habits, and tendencies that cluster together. Openness tends to be normally distributed with a small number of individuals scoring extremely high or low on the trait, and most people scoring near the average. People who score low on openness are considered to be closed to experience. They tend to be conventional and traditional in their outlook and behavior. They prefer familiar routines to new experiences, and generally have a narrower range of interests.

Self-confidence - Belief in one self and on capabilities so that, one can perform successfully keeping in mind the obstruction coming.

Openness - This factor characteristic a person is talented and intelligence, open minded and another end is Lower intellect, the simple.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Skinner, Benjiman R., (2013) Study by the relationship between confidence and performance throughout a competitive season. The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between confidence and performance throughout an entire competitive season. Two levels of confidence consistent to team sports were analyzed. Team and coach confidence were collected through the Collective Efficacy Questionnaire for Sport (CEQS) and Coaching Efficacy Scale (CES) respectively. Two teams, women's soccer and volleyball (n=48) from a college in the western United States, completed their specific questionnaires five times throughout the season. The CEQS measured collective efficacy (team confidence) and the CES measured coaching efficacy (coach confidence) for each team. Simple linear regressions were used to determine the relationship team confidence and coaching confidence had on the success of each team. Pearson's correlation coefficients were taken to determine if team and coach confidence were connected throughout the season. Volleyball was statistically significant for both team and coach confidence at $p = 0.033$ and $p = 0.040$ respectively, with a .68 correlation coefficient. Conversely, the soccer team was not statistically significant for both team and coach confidence at $p = 0.53$ and $p = 0.93$ for each. There was, however, a strong correlation coefficient at .89 for the two levels. The findings suggest that team and coach confidence may be related and associated with the success of the team. The results also hint, through the correlation coefficients, that team and coach confidence may be connected.

Martin, J. J., & Gill, D.L. (1991). The relationships among competitive orientation, sport-confidence, self-efficacy, anxiety, and performance. We examined the relationships among trait and state psychological variables and performance in male high school distance runners using the Sport Orientation Questionnaire (SOQ; GiU & Deeter, 1988), the Competitive Orientation Inventory (COI; Vealey, 1986), the Trait Sport-confidence Inventory (TSCI; Vealey, 1986), the State Sport-Confidence Inventory (SSCI; Vealey, 1986), the Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 (CSAI-2; Martens, wlrton, Vealey, Bump, & Smith, 1990), and separate self-efficacy scales for performance (time) and outcome (place). As hypothesized, trait sport-confidence predicted state sport-confidence and outcome self-efficacy. However, competitive orientation did not contribute to the prediction of state measures. State

sport confidence and self-efficacy predicted performance, as hypothesized. Surprisingly, outcome self-efficacy was a stronger predictor than performance self-efficacy, which did not contribute to the prediction of performance time or place. The runners' youth and lack of competitive track experience may have prevented them from forming accurate performance self-efficacy judgments. In contrast, the familiar and small competitive field may have allowed these athletes to form accurate outcome self-efficacy judgments.

Patrizia Steca., Dario Baretta., Andrea Greco., and Marco D'Addaria (2018) Study by Associations between personality, sports participation and athletic success. A comparison of Big Five in sporting and non-sporting adults. The present study investigates whether the Big Five personality traits are different among diverse sports populations. A sample of 881 male athletes and non-athletes completed a self-report questionnaire measuring their personality traits. The Exploratory Structure Equation Modeling (ESEM) approach is adopted to test measurement invariance and mean differences among groups. The results indicate that athletes who had experienced the most success in their sport scored higher than non-athletes in each personality dimension of the Big Five, with the exception of openness, while less successful athletes scored higher than non-athletes only in extraversion and agreeableness. The more successful athletes showed higher agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability than the less successful athletes. Individual-sport athletes were found to be more energetic and open than team-sport athletes. The current findings help clarify the relationships between personality traits, sports participation and athletic success.

Marina Shariati and Sabah Bakhtiari (2011) Study by Comparison of personality characteristics athlete and non-athlete student, Islamic Azad University of Ahvaz. In this study, researchers compared the personality characteristics (neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness and conscientiousness) non-athlete students and student athletes, Islamic Azad University of Ahvaz deals. Results showed that participation in sports has a positive effect on the personality characteristics of people. Also athletes are more positive personality characteristics than non-athletes.

Saimitra Chouhan and Dr. Shraddha Tripathi (2018) Personality attributes of sports and non- sports person: A comparative study. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in the four attributes of personality i.e. neuroticism, extroversion, conscientiousness, openness of sports and non-sports person. But a significance difference is found in the agreeableness of both the persons.

Aim of the Study -

To study the difference between self-confidence and openness among sportsperson and non-sportsperson students.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To study the difference between self-confidence of sportsperson and non-sportsperson students.
- 2) To study the difference between openness of sportsperson and non-sportsperson students.

Hypotheses of Research-

- 1) There is significant difference between self-confidence of sportsperson and non-sportsperson

students.

- 2) There is significant difference between openness of sportsperson and non-sportsperson students.

Variable of the study-

Independent Variables – 1) sportsperson students and non-sportsperson students

2) male and female

Dependent Variables - 1) Score of self-confidence 2) Score of Openness

Method

Sample:-

The sample consists of 100 subjects 50 sportsperson and 50 non-sportsperson students between ages rang 18-24 years were selected using purposive sampling technique. The data of students was collected from 50 males and 50 female's sportsperson and non-sportsperson students as M.J. College, Baheti College and D N College of Social work from Jalgaon.

Experimental Design-

Research Design-

The present study investigation is designed as 2x2 factorial design was used

Gender	Sportsperson	Non- Sportsperson	Total
Male	25	25	50
Female	25	25	50
Total	50	50	100

Tools

The data will be collected from respondents by using in Self-concept scales and The NEO five factor inventory the information about these tests is given below.

1. Self Concept Scale:

This scale was constructed by Mukta Rani Rasthogi . This scale consists of 51 items. It can be administered individually as well as to group. There is no time limit but all items can be responded within the time limit of 30 minutes. Below each statement are given five responses. Strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree.

The self-concept scale consists of ten factors. health and sex appropriateness, abilities, **self-confidence**, self-acceptance, worthiness, present past and future, beliefs and convictions, feeling of shame and guilt, sociability, emotional. The total score for the self-concept is the sum of the factor scores.

2. The NEO five factor inventory

This personality inventory was constructed by COSTA and McCrae 2010. This test consists of 60 items. It can be administered individually as well as to group. There is no time for completing the test but the respondent is advised to complete the test as quickly as possible. Below each statement are given five responses.

The NEO five factor personality inventory consists of five factor of personality- neuroticism, extraversion, **openness**, agreeableness, conscientiousness. The total score for the personality inventory is the sum of the factor scores.

Result and Discussion-

In this part investigator has explained the result related to statistical analysis and hypothesis

Hypotheses-1) There is significant difference between self-confidence of sportsperson and non-sportsperson students.

Table no. 01- Self-confidence of sportsperson and non- sportsperson students.

	Types	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	Level of significant
self-confidence	sportsperson	50	20.35	4.68	98	3.55	0.01
	Non-sportsperson	50	17.60	3.74			

The Mean Score of self-confidence among non- sportsperson and sportsperson students along with SD and 't' Value is given in table -1

As shown in the above table the mean score on the self-confidence of sportsperson students is 20.35 (SD = 4.68) as compared to the mean score of non- sportsperson students is 17.60 (SD = 3.74). The calculative 't' value is 3.55 which is significant at 0.01 levels. It means indicates that there is a significant difference between the self-confidence of sportsperson and non- sportsperson students. That's why the above hypothesis is accepted.

Hypotheses 2) There is significant difference between Openness of sportsperson and non- sportsperson students.

Table no. 02- Openness of sportsperson and non- sportsperson students.

	Faculty	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	Level of significant
Openness	sportsperson	50	27.16	5.63	98	2.10	0.05 Significant
	Non- sportsperson	50	25.13	4.90			

The Mean Score of Openness among sportsperson and non- sportsperson students along with SD and 't' Value is given in table - 2

As shown in the above table the mean score on Openness of sportsperson students is 27.16 (SD = 5.63) as compared to the mean score of non- sportsperson students is 25.13 (SD = 4.90). The calculative 't' value is 2.10 which is significant at 0.05 level. It means indicates that there is a significant difference between the Openness of sportsperson and non- sportsperson. That's why the above hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion-

The finding of the present study is that sportsperson students have better self-confidence and openness than non- sportsperson students. Sportsperson Students have more self-confidence as they are more expressive in thought than the non- sportsperson students; it means that students of the sportsperson express their emotions and feelings frankly to other people. It also shows that openness has an impact on their lifestyle and so they behave confidently.

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